

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF ANATOMICAL AND FUNCTIONAL EFFICACY OF A-VEGF THERAPY SWITCHING

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7793682>

Abstract. Macular edema is the leading cause of vision loss with the increasing prevalence of diabetes mellitus, a true epidemic in developed countries. Diabetic macular edema is closely related to lifestyle, obesity, smoking, or high blood pressure. Macular edema is the leading cause of vision loss in people with diabetes in developed countries, and its prevalence is directly related to the duration of diabetes. Its incidence figures vary from publication to publication, ranging between 7.5% and 15.2%, and are more common in patients with type 2 diabetes receiving insulin.

Keywords: diabetic macular edema, diabetes mellitus, glycemic control

Introduction. Healthcare professionals should take care to evaluate comorbid retinopathy, including DMO and proliferative retinopathy, when managing patients with diabetes. People with diabetes need to see an ophthalmologist (who can accurately assess the severity of diabetic retinopathy and determine the presence or absence of DMO at the outpatient clinic regularly. Although good blood pressure and blood sugar control can help prevent the development of diabetic retinopathy, it is not a substitute for an eye exam. Patients without a history of diabetic retinopathy are advised to have an eye exam every 1 to 2 years; patients with diabetic retinopathy with an appropriate increase in the frequency of examinations and examinations by ophthalmologists experienced in treating diabetic retinopathy.

Materials and Methods: The study groups were comparable by gender, age and concomitant pathology. All patients complained of decreased vision at the first visit. The presence of intra- and subretinal fluid as well as elevation of pigment epithelium according to OCT data were registered. According to the instructions for use of brolicizumab, all patients in the study groups underwent loading IVC with an interval of 1-2 months. After loading 3 monthly TDFs, brolicizumab in all 78 patients.

Conclusions: Moist forms of age-related macular degeneration change the structural and functional state of the visual system and on this basis, a conceptual scheme was developed which included the inclusion of pathogenetic mechanisms of the disease development.

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